

CLINICAL APPROACH IN A HEMOPHILIA PATIENT WITH HVAH IN A CENTER SPECIALIZED IN HEMATOLOGY

[Ciências da Saúde, Volume 28 - Edição 134/MAI 2024 / 23/05/2024](#)

REGISTRO DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11263604

Phamela de Freitas Geraldo Antunes¹; Daniel Antunes Pereira²; Vinícius Freitas Bastos³; Maria Clara Arca Peixoto⁴; Cássia Santos de Lima Menezes⁵; Diego de Lima Moura⁶; Antônio Carlos de Freitas da Silva⁷; Monique José de Souza Chagas⁸; Yasmin Faria Menezes Castro Santos⁹; Amanda Menescal Sias Lins¹⁰; Isaías Leite de Almeida Esteves¹¹.

ABSTRACT

This case of a 53-year-old male (MAC) diagnosed with mild hemophilia B, who presented with dysarthria, myalgia, and vomiting over four days. Initial computed tomography on 24/02/2024 revealed intraparenchymal hemorrhage with midline shift, prompting conservative treatment under neurosurgical care. Factor IX replacement therapy commenced immediately on 24/02/2024, with rigorous monitoring to ensure adequate cerebral perfusion. Despite observed hemorrhage area increase during follow-up on 26/02/2024, the patient remained neurologically intact. Continuous factor IX replacement per protocol, with adjustments in antihypertensive therapy and glycemic control, sustained stability, evidenced by subsequent CT scans on 02/03/2024 showing no further

hemorrhage progression. The case underscores the critical role of multidisciplinary collaboration among neurosurgery, intensive care, and hematology in optimizing outcomes for hemophiliac patients with severe hemorrhagic complications. Monitoring hematoma evolution through frequent imaging and meticulous therapeutic adjustments are crucial aspects of this comprehensive approach. In conclusion, this case report emphasizes the successful management of ICH in hemophilia B, reinforcing the need for personalized protocols and continuous surveillance to navigate bleeding control and thrombotic risk effectively. Future advancements in hemophilia management, including gene therapy and extended half-life factor replacements, hold promise for further enhancing outcomes and quality of life for these patients.

Keywords: *Hemophilia B, Intracranial Hemorrhages, factor IX.1*

INTRODUCTION

In Brazil, the prevalence of hemophilia A is 1 in 10,000 males, while hemophilia B affects approximately 0.7 in 35,000 males. From 1999 to 2016, a total of 927 male deaths related to hemophilia were recorded, with 45.1% of these deaths having hemophilia as the underlying cause and 54.9% as an associated cause. The leading cause associated with deaths where hemophilia was the underlying cause was hemorrhage, particularly intracranial hemorrhage (ICH), which poses a significant challenge due to its high mortality and morbidity rates. ICH is especially prevalent among hemophiliacs, with an incidence of 2.2% to 7.7%, which is at least 20 times higher than in the general male population. Risk factors include severe disease, on-demand treatment, presence of inhibitors, and cranial trauma (DE CRISTOFARO; FRANCHINI, 2019; DIRINGER et al., 2008; SANTO, 2021).

In children with hemophilia, ICH can occur spontaneously or as a result of unwitnessed trauma, making it difficult to assess its exact prevalence. Literature reviews indicate that most cases of ICH in hemophilic children

occur in those with severe hemophilia A, with a median age of 2 years. Symptoms of ICH in children can be nonspecific, with alterations in consciousness and headache being the most frequent. In children under 2 years old, symptoms such as seizures, pallor, bulging fontanelle, vomiting, and irritability are common. In older children, headache, alterations in consciousness, and neurological deficits are predominant. Early identification and proper management are crucial to minimize adverse consequences of ICH in these patients(LJUNG; MATINO; SHAPIRO, 2024; ROHAERT; LABARQUE, 2021).

Treatment of hemophilia B has significantly evolved in recent years with the introduction of extended half-life factor IX (FIX) replacement products. These products, such as rFIXFc, a recombinant fusion protein with extended circulation time, provide effective protection against bleeding with less frequent administrations, improving quality of life for patients. rFIXFc has a biodistribution profile that supports hemostasis at vascular injury sites regardless of activity levels(CHO et al., 2016; CHOU; HSU; LIN, 2023; DIRINGER et al., 2008; LJUNG; MATINO; SHAPIRO, 2024).

Spontaneous intracranial hemorrhage is a rare complication of hemophilia, occurring at a frequency of 2.2% to 7.8% with a mortality rate of 34%. This condition is potentially fatal and requires emergent neurosurgical intervention. Small hemorrhages without significant mass effect can be managed conservatively with factor VIII concentrate and rigorous neurological monitoring. However, larger hemorrhages require surgery under factor VIII coverage. A specific case successfully converted an acute subdural hematoma into a chronic one using decongestants and factor VIII concentrate, thereby avoiding the need for craniotomy and significantly reducing the risk of re-bleeding. Intensive factor VIII management followed guidelines from the World Federation of Hemophilia, with precisely calculated doses to maintain therapeutic levels during the perioperative period, demonstrating favorable functional outcomes with a Glasgow score of 5(FERNANDES et al., 2021; OLDENBURG et al., 2023).

In contrast, significant advances in gene therapy for hemophilia B were achieved in 2011 by Nathwani et al. This pioneering study used an AAV vector with hepatic tropism to deliver and sustain expression of the F9 gene in patients, raising factor IX levels up to 6%. Optimized self-complementary DNA constructs improved expression efficiency, allowing for a single non-invasive intravenous infusion rather than intrahepatic injections. However, sustained expression was challenged by immune clearance of transduced hepatocytes, mitigated in this study by using steroids to suppress the immune response. These advances offer promising prospects for future treatments of hemophilia B, potentially radically altering the management of this chronic condition (FERNANDES et al., 2021; LJUNG; MATINO; SHAPIRO, 2024; ROCINO; FRANCHINI; COPPOLA, 2017).

This case report aims to discuss a case of ICH in a patient with hemophilia B managed conservatively by neurosurgery and therapeutic management with factor IX replacement, resulting in a good outcome.

CASE REPORT

MAC, male, 53 years old, diagnosed with mild hemophilia B, presented with a clinical picture evolving over four days characterized by dysarthria, myalgia, and vomiting. Following initial evaluation and a computed tomography scan on 24/02/2024, he was diagnosed with intraparenchymal hemorrhage with midline shift, conservatively treated by the neurosurgical team (Figure 1). Factor IX replacement therapy was initiated on 24/02, and he was kept under rigorous monitoring, highlighting compensatory hypertension to ensure adequate cerebral perfusion. NIHSS 5, previously in good health, GLASGOW 15, disoriented and without neurological deficit, Aplastic anemia, chronic kidney disease, started nifedipine and Dexamethasone and rigorous glycemic monitoring. Despite increased hemorrhagic area observed on follow-up CT on 26/02, the patient remained oriented, without significant neurological deficits. In subsequent follow-up, the patient continued to receive factor IX

replacement per protocol, with adjustments in antihypertensive therapy and glycemic control. CT scan on 02/03 showed no further increase in hemorrhage, indicating stability (Figure 2). Management was reassessed in conjunction with intensive care and hematology, emphasizing the importance of clinical and radiological vigilance, especially in the face of any neurological deterioration.

Finally, after 10 days of factor IX replacement and stabilization of clinical condition, the patient demonstrated a good overall and neurological outcome.

Figure 1 – red arrow, intraparenchymal bleeding with discrete midline shift.

Figure 2 – blue arrow, intraparenchymal bleeding with discrete midline shift. maintaining standard and without increasing injury.

DISCUSSION

Intracerebral hemorrhage (ICH) is a rare but severe complication of hemophilia, affecting between 2.2% to 7.7% of patients with the condition, a significantly higher incidence than in the general population. In the case of the 53-year-old patient with mild hemophilia B, the presentation of ICH

with midline shift required careful management due to its complexity. The initial conservative approach with factor IX replacement was crucial, given the need to stabilize hemorrhage without resorting to immediate invasive procedures, reflecting management guidelines for hemophiliac patients with intracranial hemorrhages (HEGDE; NAIR; UPADHYAYA, 2016; ROHAERT; LABARQUE, 2021).

Case reports and previous studies indicate that while factor IX administration may reduce hematoma expansion and improve outcomes in ICH cases in hemophilia B, there is an associated increased risk of arterial thromboembolic events, especially at higher doses. This risk is particularly relevant in older patients with a higher prevalence of atherosclerosis and reduced mobility, such as the patient in question. Therefore, the decision for conservative management with factor IX may have been influenced by the balance between hemostatic efficacy and the risk of thromboembolic complications.

In neonates and children with hemophilia, the incidence of ICH is high in the first few days of life, with high mortality. In adults, risk factors for ICH include hypertension, presence of inhibitors, infections such as HIV and hepatitis C, and inadequate adherence to prophylaxis. In the discussed patient, arterial hypertension was managed with nitroprusside, maintaining blood pressure at controlled levels to minimize the risk of re-bleeding, while factor IX replacement was carefully adjusted to ensure adequate therapeutic levels (BADESCU et al., 2022; LJUNG; MATINO; SHAPIRO, 2024).

The literature suggests that intensive and personalized management of ICH in hemophiliacs is crucial to prevent adverse outcomes. Frequent imaging such as CT scans allowed monitoring of hematoma evolution and adjustment of therapy as needed. Maintenance of factor IX replacement and continuous monitoring of renal function and glucose levels demonstrate the need for a rigorous multidisciplinary

approach(HEGDE; NAIR; UPADHYAYA, 2016; LJUNG; MATINO; SHAPIRO, 2024; SANTO, 2021).

CONCLUSION

This patient's case illustrates the complexity of managing ICH in hemophiliacs, highlighting the importance of an approach that balances hemorrhage control with prevention of thromboembolic complications. Success in stabilizing the hemorrhagic condition without significant hematoma increase until 02/03, coupled with the absence of neurological deficits, reflects the effectiveness of the adopted management. This report reinforces the need for personalized protocols and continuous surveillance to optimize outcomes in patients with hemophilia and severe hemorrhagic complications.

REFERENCES

BADESCU, M. C. et al. Current Therapeutic Approach to Atrial Fibrillation in Patients with Congenital Hemophilia. **Journal of personalized medicine**, v. 12, n. 4, 1 abr. 2022.

CHO, J. Y. et al. Clinical Characteristics and Prognostic Factors in Hemophiliacs with Intracranial Hemorrhage: A Single-Center, Retrospective Experience. **Indian journal of hematology & blood transfusion: an official journal of Indian Society of Hematology and Blood Transfusion**, v. 32, n. 4, p. 488–493, 1 dez. 2016.

CHOU, S. C.; HSU, Y. C.; LIN, S. W. Gene therapy for hemophilia, a clinical viewpoint. **Journal of the Formosan Medical Association = Taiwan yi zhi**, v. 122, n. 11, p. 1101–1110, 1 nov. 2023.

DE CRISTOFARO, R.; FRANCHINI, M. Intracranial haemorrhage in children and adults with haemophilia A and B: a literature review of the last 20 years. **Blood transfusion = Trasfusione del sangue**, v. 17, n. 5, p. 334–335, 2019.

DIRINGER, M. N. et al. Risk of thromboembolic events in controlled trials of rFVIIa in spontaneous intracerebral hemorrhage. **Stroke**, v. 39, n. 3, p. 850–856, mar. 2008.

FERNANDES, J. M. A. et al. Factor VIII prophylactic therapy reduces neurological complications in patients with Hemophilia A. **Arquivos de neuro-psiquiatria**, v. 79, n. 12, p. 1116–1122, 1 dez. 2021.

HEGDE, A.; NAIR, R.; UPADHYAYA, S. Spontaneous intracerebral hemorrhage in hemophiliacs-A treatment dilemma. **International journal of surgery case reports**, v. 29, p. 17–19, 2016.

LJUNG, R.; MATINO, D.; SHAPIRO, A. D. Recombinant factor IX Fc for the treatment of hemophilia B. **European journal of haematology**, v. 112, n. 5, p. 678–691, 1 maio 2024.

OLDENBURG, J. et al. Clinical experience of switching patients with severe hemophilia to rVIII-SingleChain or rIX-FP. **Current medical research and opinion**, v. 39, n. 2, p. 219–225, 2023.

ROCINO, A.; FRANCHINI, M.; COPPOLA, A. Treatment and Prevention of Bleeds in Haemophilia Patients with Inhibitors to Factor VIII/IX. **Journal of clinical medicine**, v. 6, n. 4, 1 abr. 2017.

ROHAERT, C.; LABARQUE, V. Spontaneous intracranial haemorrhage as initial presentation of haemophilia in infants and children: A case report and systematic literature review. **Haemophilia: the official journal of the World Federation of Hemophilia**, v. 27, n. 3, p. e398–e401, 1 maio 2021.

SANTO, A. H. Causes of death and mortality trends related to hemophilia in Brazil, 1999 to 2016. **Hematology, transfusion and cell therapy**, v. 43, n. 2, p. 171–178, 1 abr. 2021.

- ¹Discente do Curso Superior de Medicina da Universidade Iguazu *Campus Nova Iguazu* e-mail: phamellafreitas@hotmail.com
- ²Discente do Curso Superior de Medicina da Universidade Iguazu *Campus Nova Iguazu* e-mail: danielantunespi@gmail.com
- ³Discente do Curso Superior de Medicina da Universidade Iguazu *Campus Nova Iguazu* e-mail: vinicius.freitas16@icloud.com
- ⁴Discente do Curso Superior de Medicina da Universidade Iguazu *Campus Nova Iguazu* e-mail: maria.arcapeixoto@gmail.com
- ⁵Discente do Curso Superior de Medicina da Universidade Iguazu *Campus Nova Iguazu* e-mail: cassiasantosedelimamenezes@gmail.com
- ⁶Discente do Curso Superior de Medicina da Universidade Iguazu *Campus Nova Iguazu* e-mail: ddelimamoura@gmail.com
- ⁷Discente do Curso Superior de Medicina da Universidade Iguazu *Campus Nova Iguazu* e-mail: antoniofreitascff@gmail.com
- ⁸Discente do Curso Superior de Medicina da Universidade Iguazu *Campus Nova Iguazu* e-mail: moniqjsc@gmail.com
- ⁹Discente do Curso Superior de Medicina da Universidade Iguazu *Campus Nova Iguazu* e-mail: yasminfaria@gmail.com
- ¹⁰Discente do Curso Superior de Medicina da Universidade Iguazu *Campus Nova Iguazu* e-mail: amandasias@gmail.com
- ¹¹Discente do Curso Superior de Medicina da Universidade Iguazu *Campus Nova Iguazu* e-mail: isaias.esteves1702@gmail.com

[← Post anterior](#)

RevistaFT

A RevistaFT têm 28 anos. É uma **Revista Científica Eletrônica Multidisciplinar Indexada de Alto Impacto e Qualis “B2”**.

Contato

Queremos te ouvir.
WhatsApp RJ:
(21) 98159-7352

Conselho Editorial

Editores
Fundadores:
Dr. Oston de

Periodicidade mensal e de acesso livre. Leia gratuitamente todos os artigos e publique o seu também [clikando aqui.](#)

ou 98275-4439

WhatsApp SP:

(11) 98597-3405

e-Mail:

contato@revistaf
t.com.br

ISSN: 1678-0817

CNPJ:

48.728.404/0001-
22

**FI= 5.397 (muito
alto)**

Fator de impacto é um método bibliométrico para avaliar a importância de periódicos científicos em suas respectivas áreas. Uma medida que reflete o número médio de citações de artigos científicos publicados em determinado periódico, criado por Eugene Garfield, em que os de maior FI

Lacerda Mendes.

Dr. João Marcelo
Gigliotti.

Editor

Científico:

Dr. Oston de
Lacerda Mendes

Orientadoras:

Dra. Hevellyn
Andrade
Monteiro
Dra. Chimene
Kuhn Nobre

Revisores:

Lista atualizada periodicamente em revistaft.com.br/expanded. Venha fazer parte de nosso time de revisores também!

são considerados
mais
importantes.

Copyright © Revista ft Ltda. 1996 -
2024

Rua José Linhares, 134 - Leblon | Rio
de Janeiro-RJ | Brasil